

Assessing the Impacts of in effective Communication Skill in Teaching and Learning Process in English Classroom the Case of Second Year English Language and Literature Major Students at Debre Tabor University

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ABSTRACT: *The main purpose of this study was assessing the impacts of ineffective communication skill in teaching and learning process in English classroom in the case of second year English language and literature major students at Debre Tabor University in 2010 E.C. The target populations of this study were second year English language and literature major students and English language and literature major teachers who were assigned to teach at second year English major students. The researcher used 25 students and 3 English language teachers in the sample. The students were selected using comprehensive sampling technique whereas English language teachers were selected using purposive sampling technique. To collect data, the researcher used questionnaire, interview and classroom observation. Then the researcher used quantitative and qualitative approaches to analyzed and interpreted the data which were obtained from data collection instruments. The finding of the research showed that students failed to communicate effectively in the teaching and learning process in English classroom. Finally based on the finding, it was recommended that in order to improve effective communication in the classroom, students should have intrinsic motivation, teachers should use English language in the classroom rather than using other language and the University should avoid noise of communication which found around the classroom.*

Keywords: *Impact, infective, noise of communication, intrinsic motivation*

I. Introduction

1.1. Background of the Study

Communication is the happenings of respondents of someone to the behavior of another person (Lorry, et al. 1997).

Communication is the activity of conveying information through the exchange of ideas, feelings, intentions, expectations, perceptions or commands by speech, writing, and gesture and by other means between two or more participants (Nilanjana pal, et al.2016).

Communication plays a great role in education. It is an instrument for teacher to teacher, teacher to student, student to student, teacher to parent, teacher to administrator, administrator to parent or vice-versa, communication is importance to make sure our students to be successful (David Andrade, 2015).

According to Delia Muste (2016), classroom is a complex communication space. Communication process involves verbal, non-verbal, para-verbal components and is designed to mediate students to teacher. Effective communication, especially in educational field is based on the ability to express one's own ideas and views clearly with confidence and permanently adapting his or her content and style to the class. Interaction between teachers and students can contribute to effective communication in the classroom or may be the source of problematic situations if it is Ineffective.

Ineffective communication impedes someone from his or her normal achievement of the goals he or she has. Ineffective communication means not having the intended outcome and communication means to convey an idea or thought to someone. So ineffective communication means attempting to communicate something, but it is being received differently than one intended. It is our responsibility to tailor our communication for the person listening if we wish for the correct message to be received. When communication does not fulfill, it is ineffective. Requirements are a stronger form of intentions, implying there are negative consequences or penalties if they are not met (John Joseph, etal.2016).

II. Research Methodology

2. 1 Research Design

The aim of this study was to assess the impacts of ineffective communication skills in teaching and learning process. The study employed descriptive survey research design. Because descriptive survey research design allowed the researcher to analyze and interpret data both quantitatively and qualitatively.

2. 2 Target Populations

The target populations of this study were second year English language and literature major students and English language and literature major teachers who were assigned to teach at second year English major students at Debre Tabor University in 2010 E.C.

2. 3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

There were twenty-five second year English language and literature major students and four English language and literature major teachers who were assigned to teach at English major students at Debre Tabor University in 2010 E.C. From the total of twenty-five students, there were twenty-one male students and four female students and the researcher took total of twenty-five in the sample using comprehensive sampling techniques and used to conduct a study on small numbers of populations. On the other hand, the researcher took three teachers from four English major teachers since one teacher was not voluntary. So using purposive sampling techniques the researchers took three teachers.

2. 4 Source of Data

The researcher gathered data using primary sources. The primary sources of data were second year English language and literature major students and English language and literature major teachers who taught second year English major students at Debre Tabor University.

2. 5 Data Gathering Tools

The researcher conducted the study by gathering relevant information through preparing data gathering tools like questionnaire, interview and direct classroom observation.

2. 6 Data Gathering Procedures

2. 6. 1 Questionnaire

The researcher used questionnaire as the main tools of data collection for this research. The researcher prepared close ended and open ended questionnaire for the students to get relevant information from the respondents about the impacts of ineffective communication skill on students in teaching and learning process in English classroom.

2. 6. 2 Interview

Next to questionnaire the researcher gathered relevant data through preparing interview's questionnaire for English major teachers. So the researcher took three English major teachers who were assigned to teach second year English major student's using purposive sampling for the interview. The researcher prepared semi structured interview questions for the interviewee.

2. 6. 3 Observation

The researcher gathered additional data through direct observation in the classroom. So the researcher prepared observation checklist and attended classroom discussion. This direct observation in the classroom helped the researcher to get additional information for their research. The researcher observed classroom discussions three times in the classroom.

2. 7 Methods of Data Analysis and Interpretation

In this study, the data that gathered through open ended questionnaire, interviews and observation were analyzed and interpreted qualitatively using descriptive statement and the data that gathered through close ended questionnaire was analyzed quantitatively using percentage.

III. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Data obtained from the sample students and teachers through questionnaire, interview and classroom observation is analyzed and interpreted as follows.

3.1. Data Analysis on Students Close Ended Questionnaire

Respondent's background information

Department= English

Sex: male=21 Female=4

Year= Second year

(Inthe following discussion, **No** = represents Number,**F** = represents Frequency and **%** = represents Percentage).

Strongly agree=5 Agree=4 Neutral=3 Disagree=2 Strongly disagree=1

Table 1: Student's feeling about ineffective communication skill in teaching and learning process.

No	Items	Responses													
		Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total		mean	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
1.	I feel that ineffective communication skill affects teaching and learning process in classroom.	10	40	15	60	-	-	-	-	-	-	25	100	110	4.4

A. Table (1), as it is shown in the table above, 10 (40%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they feel ineffective communication skill affects teaching and learning process in classroom and 15(60%) of the respondents agreed that ineffective communication skill affects teaching and learning process in classroom. This shows, all the respondents feel that ineffective communication skill affects teaching and learning process in classroom. As the mean score indicated that majority of the respondents agreed ineffective communication affects teaching and learning in English classroom. In line with this, the observation result showed that students are unable to communicate effectively.

2. Student's readiness to communicate with English in classroom.

No	Items	Responses													
		Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total		mean	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
2.	I always ready to communicate with English in classroom.	8	32	10	40	2	8	3	12	2	8	25	100	94	3.76

B. Table (2), as it is shown in the table above, 8(32%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they always ready to communicate with English in classroom and 10 (40%) of the respondents agreed that they always ready to communication with English in classroom. However, 2 (8%) of the respondents are neutral. On the other hand, 3 (12%) of the respondents disagreed on this and 2 (8%) of the respondents strongly disagreed. This indicates that 72% of the respondents are always ready to communicate with English in classroom. So based on the mean score, the researcher conclude that majority of the respondents agreed that they always ready to communicate with English in classroom.

3. Student's feeling about asking questions with English.

No	Items	Responses													
		Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total		mean	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
3.	I feel that asking questions with in English helps me to develop my communication skill.	16	64	8	32	-	-	1	4	-	-	25	100	98	3.9

C.Table (3), as it is indicated in the table above, 16 (64) of the respondents strongly agreed that they feel asking questions with English helps them to develop their communication skill and 8 (32) of the respondents agreed that they feel asking questions with English helps them to develop their communication skill whereas 1 (4%)of the respondent disagreed that asking questions with English does not help to develop communication skill. From this, the researcherconcludes that almost 96% of the respondents feel that asking questions with English helps them to develop their communication skill and the mean score indicated that majority of the respondents agreed they feel asking questions help them to develop their communication skill.

4. Student's feeling about answering questions by English.

No	Items	Responses													
		Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total		mean	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
4.	I feel that answering questions by English helps me to develop my communication skill.	16	64	9	36	-	-	-	-	-	-	25	100	116	4.64

D.Table (4), as it is stated in the table above, 16(64) of the respondents strongly agreed that they feel answering questions by English helps them to develop their communication skill and 9(36) of the respondents agreed that answering questions by English helps them to develop their communication skill. Therefore, one can conclude that all the respondents feel that answering questions by English helps them to develop their communication skill and the mean score showed that most students strongly agreed that answering question by English help them to develop their communication skill.

5. Student's motivation to communicate with their teachers and class mates.

No	Items	Responses													
		Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total		mean	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	No	%	F	%		
5.	I have high motivation to communicate with my classmates and teachers.	-	-	4	16	4	16	7	28	10	40	25	100	52	2.08

E. Table (5), as it is shown in the table above, 4 (16%) of the respondents agreed that they have high motivation to communicate with their class mates and teachers. 4 (16%) of the respondents are neutral. But 7 (28%) of the respondents disagreed or they have not high motivation to communicate with their class mates and teachers. And 10 (40%) of the respondents strongly disagreed on this or they have low motivation to communicate with their class mates and teachers. Then the researcher concludes, 68% or majority of the respondents have low motivation to communicate with their class mates and teachers. Since they have low motivation, they are ineffective in their communication skill and the mean showed that majority of the respondents disagreed or they have low motivation.

6. Student's relation with their teachers and class mates.

No	Items	Responses													
		Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total		mean	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
6.	I always have smooth relation with my teachers and classmates.	7	28	14	56	1	4	3	12	-	-	25	100	100	4

F. Table (6), as it is indicated in the table above, 7(28) of the respondents strongly agreed that they always have smooth relation with their teachers and class mates and 14(56) of the respondents agreed that they always have smooth relation with their teachers and class mates. From the respondents 1(4%) of the respondent is neutral. However, 3 (12%) of the respondents disagreed or they have not smooth relation with their teachers and class mates. Therefore, 84% or majority of the respondents always have smooth relation with their teachers and class mates. On the other hand, 16% or some of the respondents do not have smooth relation with their teachers and class mates. Then the researcher concludes from the mean, majority of the respondents have smooth relation whereas some of the respondents have not smooth relation.

7. Student's responses on noises of communication which affect them

No	Items	Responses													
		Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total		mean	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
7	There are noises which affect me when I am learning in classroom.	11	44	11	44	-	-	2	8	1	4	25	100	104	4.16

G. Table (7), as it is stated in the table above, 11 (44%) of the respondents strongly agreed that there are noises of communication which affect them when they are learning in classroom. In the same percentage or 11(44%) of the respondents agreed that there are noises of communication which affect them when they are learning. In contrast, 2 (8%) of the respondents disagreed or there are no noises which affect them when they are learning and 1 (4) of the respondent strongly disagreed on this. The researcher can conclude from the mean result; majority of the respondents are affected by noises. However, 12% or some respondents are not affected by noises. So majority of the respondents are ineffective communicator due to the noises of communication around the class.

8. Student's responses on how they understand what their teachers say in English.

No	Items	Responses													
		Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total		mean	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
8.	I always easily understand what my teachers say in English.	7	28	1	4	-	-	7	28	10	40	25	100	70	2.8

H. Table (8), As it is shown in the table above, 7 (28) of the respondent strongly agreed that they always easily understand what teachers say in English and 1 (4%) of the respondents agreed that he or she always easily understand what teachers say in English whereas 7 (28%) of the respondents disagreed and 10 (40%) of the respondents strongly disagreed on this. Therefore, the researcher concludes that 68% or majority of the respondents cannot easily understand what their teachers say in English. So the mean showed that they are neutral in their communication, but 32% or some respondents are effective because they always easily understand what their teachers say in English. From this one can understand that majority of students are neutral to communicate.

9. Student's attitude towards English classroom

No	Items	Responses													
		Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total		Mean	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
9.	I have positive attitude towards English classroom.	11	44	12	48	-	-	2	8	-	-	25	100	107	4.28

I. Table(9), as it is indicated in the table above, 11 (48%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they have positive attitude towards English classroom and 12 (48%) of the respondents agreed that they have positive attitude towards English classroom. On the other hand, 2 (8%) of the respondents disagreed or they have not positive attitude towards English classroom. The researcher concludes that 92% or nearly all the respondents have positive attitude and few or 8% of the respondents have not positive attitude or they have negative attitude towards English classroom. The mean indicated that majority of the respondents have positive attitude towards English classroom.

10. Student's thinking about communication in teaching and learning process.

No	Items	Responses													
		Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total		Mean	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
10.	I always think that communication in classroom facilitates teaching and learning process.	12	48	11	44	-	-	2	8	-	-	25	100	108	4.32

J. Table (10), As it is stated in the table above, 12 (48%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they always think that communication in classroom facilitate teaching and learning process and 11 (44%) of the respondents agreed that they always think that communication in classroom facilitate teaching and learning process. But 2 (8%) of the respondents disagreed or they do not think that communication in classroom facilitate teaching and learning process. Based on the mean, one can conclude that most of the students are always think that communication facilitates teaching and learning processes. In other words, they agreed on this

4.2. Data Analysis and Interpretation on Student's Open Ended Questionnaire

1. Respondent's responses on what are the factors that makes you ineffective communicator in English classroom?

As majority of the respondents said factors that makes them ineffective communicator in English classroom includes: limited vocabulary knowledge, lack of motivation, low grammar knowledge, influences of mother tongue, poor self-confidence and lack of experiences make them ineffective communicator in English classroom. The researcher agreed on these factors because there were factors that observed by the researcher during direct classroom observation. The researcher observed that limited vocabulary knowledge and the influences of mother tongue factors observed in the same way in classroom observations and most teachers responded during their interview that mother tongue influences students in English classroom communication. In addition, as the researcher observed that during classroom presentation most students used their mother tongue.

2. Respondent's responses on do you think that there are noises of communication around your classroom?If yes, how they affect you and mention them.

As majority of the respondents expressed, yes there are noises of communication around their classroom and they said that noises affect them as interfering factors during in teaching and learning process and the main noises of communication that affect them includes: sound of generator, students who move from place to place during their spare time are noises that occurred around their classroom. They disturbed them by speaking loudly. The researcher conclude that it is true there are noises of communication that disturbed student's classroom communication. The researcher assured, the main factors that disturbed classroom communication is the sound from generator as the researcher observed during classroom observations.

3. Respondent's responses on how do you express your motivation of communication?

Most respondents responded that they have low motivation and interest towards communication in classroom. This shows that they are ineffective communicator since they have low motivation. The researcher also observed that during their classroom observation that students have low motivation.

4. Respondent's responses on what do you think about the possible solutions for you to be effective in your communication skill in English classroom and what are the possible ways of teaching that teachers shall use in classroom?

As most respondents stated, the possible solutions for them to be effective in their communication skill in English classroom includes: increasing vocabulary knowledge by reading different materials, practicing English communication in classroom, to improve communication using English Language Improvement Center, avoid negative perception towards English and avoid poor self-confidence during communication are some possible solutions that suggested by majority of the respondents and most respondents stated that the possible ways of teaching that teachers shall use in English classroom are, teachers shall give necessary activities via English, teachers shall motivate the students to participate in the classroom during their class activities, teachers shall always use English and teachers shall give equal chances for each students to speak English in classroom are the possible ways of teaching that teachers shall use in English classroom are expressed by majority respondents. The researcher supported these ideas since the ideas have relation with the ideas that gathered through teacher's interview.

4.3. Data Analysis and Interpretation Gained Through Teachers Interview

1. How do you see the motivation of students for their communication?

In the interview from three teachers, two teachers stated that some students have motivation to communicate with English, but many students do not have motivation and one teacher responded, all students do not have motivation to communicate with English in classroom. These responses show that many students have low motivation to communicate with English in classroom. The researcher accepted this idea because he observed low motivation of students for their communication.

2. How do you motivate your students to communicate with English?

As two teachers responded, they motivate their students by asking brain storming questions and they try to make it clear if the questions make their students to be confused. One teacher responded, he motivates his students by allow them to read materials, let them to analysis literature texts. The researcher concludes that all teachers motivate their students by using different mechanisms.

3. What are the advantages of practicing with English in classroom for the students?

As one teacher stated, the advantages of practice with English for students are it helps them to understand each other and it is essential in terms of group work and one teacher also expressed that it is essential for mutual understanding and helps them to develop their individual performance. The other teacher responded that it helps them to improve their communication skill and it helps them to gain information or message from their instructors as well as their classmates easily. The researcher concludes that as all teachers expressed that practicing with English in classroom has many advantages for the students.

4. What do you think about the factors that makes the students to be ineffective in English classroom?

As teachers stated, there are different factors that makes the students to be ineffective in English classroom. One teacher stated that influences of mother tongue, low motivation by teachers or some teachers use mother tongue

rather than English and students do not have exposure. The second respondent teacher responded that Students low interest for communication. And also the other respondent expressed that background knowledge of students and low practice. Based on the three teacher's responses, the researcher concludes that factors raised from both sides of Students and teachers are real factors.

5. How do you express the impacts of ineffective communication for teaching and learning process?

Two teachers explained, the impacts of ineffective communication for teaching and learning is very hazard. Ineffective communication affects students' academic performance and Students can not able to understand what teachers say so that they miss the information. The other teacher stated that Students do not engage in the real world if they communicate ineffective. From this the researcher concludes that ineffective communication affects students' academic performance and make them out of the real world.

6. What do you think about the possible solutions for the Students to be effective in their communication?

One teacher responded that the possible solutions for the students to be effective in their communication is teachers should use various teaching methods such as raising questions and give class activities. Another one teacher responded, teachers should devise activities and incorporate different assignment and the other respondents stated, students should have speech community. That means they should practice communication with English where they present in the community and they should use English Language Improvement Center to improve their communication skill. The researcher suggested that the possible solutions for the students to be effective in their communication is they should motivate themselves to practice English when they present anywhere.

Data Analysis and Interpretation Gained Through Classrooms Observations

The researcher observed in classroom during teaching and learning process in order to assess the impacts of ineffective communication skill in English classroom. The researcher analyzed the observation as follows:

Researcher's observation in English classroom for students (Al= represents always, of= represents often, St= represents sometimes and Ra= represents rarely)

No	Activities	Times											
		Day 1				Day2				Day3			
		Al	Of	St	Ra	Al	Of	St	Ra	Al	Of	St	Ra
1.	Do instructors give Give correction while Students commit mistakes?				X				x				x
2.	Do instructors give class activity and ask them to present with English at the end?			x				x					X
3.	Do instructors use other language rather than English?		x				x				x		
4.	Do instructors give chance for students to speak other language?		x					x			x		

A.Table (11), Question 1: As the researcher observed in classroom, instructors gave rarely while students commit mistakes. The researcher conclude that it is bad because students do not develop effective communication skill if teachers do not give correction while they commit mistakes.

B.As indicated table (11) Question 2 above: the researcher observed that instructors sometimes give class activities, and they sometimes ask students to present with English at the end. From this the researcher concludes that the instructors should always give class activities and ask students to present with English at the end to encourage their students to be effective communicator.

C.Table (11), Question 3: As the researcher observed in classroom, instructors use mother tongue rather than English. This shows that there is the relationship between teacher’s interview responses and the researcher observation and it indicates that teachers do not motivate their students to communicate with English because they use mother tongue.

D.Table (11), Question 4: As the researchers observed that instructors often give chances for the students to speak other language. This indicates, teachers do not motivate their students to speak with English. This leads the students to be ineffective communicator in English.

Researcher’s observation in English classroom for instructors (Al= represents always, Of= represents often, St= represents sometimes and Ra= represents rarely).

No	Activities	Times											
		Day1				Day2				Day3			
		Al	Of	St	Ra	Al	Of	St	Ra	Al	Of	St	Ra
1	Do students feel confident while they speak English?				X				x				x
2	Do they present their tasks using English?			x				x				X	
3	Do they have grammatical, tense and vocabulary problems when they speak English?	x				x				x			
4	Do students motivate themselves to communicate with English in classroom?				X				x				x

A.Table (12), Question 1: as the researchers observed, students feel confident rarely while they speak English. This result indicates that there is relationship between the data that gained from open ended questionnaire. As the students responded, lack of confidence is one factor that makes them ineffective communicator. This factor assured by the researchers during classroom observation.

B.Table (12), Question 2: as the researchers observed that students present their tasks using English sometimes. This indicates, they have low motivation as the teachers explained in the interview. This implies that students are ineffective in communication in English classroom.

C.Table (12), Question 3: as the researchers observed, students always have grammatical, tense and vocabulary problems when they speak English. This leads them ineffective communicator and it has negative impacts on their academic performance.

D.Table (12), Question 4: as the researchers observed that students rarely motivate themselves to communicate with English in classroom. It indicates that students have low motivation. This result also related with teacher's response that as they stated that students have low motivation of communication.

Generally, when the researcher observed, instructors gave different activities for the students. For example, students were given text analysis assignment and asked to present it in classroom. As the researchers observed their communication during the presentation, they are ineffective in their communication skill. They have grammatical, tense, vocabulary problems and they use mother tongue. This indicates that it is related with the data that gathered through questionnaire and interview. Thus the researchers can conclude that students are ineffective communicator, and this ineffective communications skill affects students' academic performance since they missed important information.

Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusion

After assessing the impacts of ineffective communication skill in teaching and learning process in English classroom, the researchers come up with some conclusion based on the related findings of the study. The findings gained from data of questionnaire, interview and classroom observation and the researchers reached on the following conclusion.

The influences of mother tongue, low motivation, limited vocabulary knowledge, lack of self-confidence, lack of experience, background knowledge and noises of communication that found around their classroom makes the students to be ineffective in their communication. Some teachers also use mother tongue and allow the students to speak with their mother tongue too. This leads that students become ineffective communicator. So when students are ineffective communicator, there are impacts on teaching and learning process in their classroom lessons. The main impacts of ineffective communication skill in teaching and learning process in English classroom students can not able to understand what their teachers say, and this affects them on their academic performance and even they do not engage in the real world communication if they are ineffective in their communication skill. So the result was students failed to communicate effectively with English in classroom.

5.2. Recommendations

This study was conducted to assess the impacts of ineffective communication skill in teaching and learning process in English classroom the case of second year English language and literature major students at Debre Tabor University. After conducted the study, the researcher gave recommendations based on the findings or results that gained through questionnaire, interview and classroom observation. The following constructive recommendations were given based on the results.

- Both the students and the teachers have responsibilities to avoid the impacts of ineffective communication skill in teaching and learning process in English classroom.
- Teachers should motivate students to speak in English not only in classroom, but also they should encourage their students to speak with English at anywhere.
- Teachers should always use English in and out of the classroom.
- Teachers should encourage their students by providing more teaching methodology like using audio record.
- Students should try to communicate with English at any time even though they are not perfect.
- Students should increase their communication experiences by communicating with English in their everyday life.
- Students should develop intrinsic motivation to improve their communication skill. They must motivate themselves to use English everywhere.

- The University also should avoid noises of communication that disturbed the students during their classroom lessons. For example, generator energy should be replaced by solar system.

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